

THE ELECTROCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF PALMITIC ACID HYDROSOLS.

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The study of the electrochemical properties of colloidal solutions of acidic substances has received considerable attention in recent years. Colloidal solutions are often treated as homogeneous systems possessing the properties of acids in true solution (Pauli and Valko, "Elektrochemie der Kolloide," 1929; Buchner, "Colloid Chemistry" by Alexander 1926, pp. 126-136). The work of Mukherjee and co-workers (a connected account of their work and references to literature have been given in a paper by J.N. Mukherjee, R. P. Mitra and S. Mukherjee, to be published shortly in the transactions of the National Institute of Sciences of India) on the other hand has drawn attention to their polyphase character and to the part played by the electrical double layer in such systems. Investigations on silicic acid sols and on acid clay sols have shown that interactions of these systems with electrolytes consist mainly of interchanges of ions present in the electrical double layer surrounding the particles. The present investigation on colloidal solutions of palmitic acid was undertaken with a view to examine its behaviour in the light of the above theoretical stand-points.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Palmitic Acid Sol.—Pure palmitic acid (Kahlbaum) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (Merck's Reagent) so as to obtain a saturated solution. The clear solution was added drop by drop to boiling conductivity water (specific conductivity 1.3×10^{-6} mho). Part of the palmitic acid, instead of being dispersed colloiddally, floated on the surface in the form of solid particles. The sol was boiled for about 2 hours in order to drive off the alcohol. It was stocked, while hot, in the stocking vessel in an atmosphere of pure hydrogen. Fine sols without visible aggregates were obtained. The sol remained unchanged for about 10 days during which the measurements were made. On keeping for a longer period, aggregates begin to appear.

The stocking vessel.—The apparatus consists of a Jena glass bottle fitted with a normal burette by a ground-glass joint. It is so devised that

tic sol can be stocked and transferred in an atmosphere of hydrogen gas without coming in contact with atmospheric air. The sol comes in contact only with Pyrex and Jena normal glass surfaces and the system of glass apparatus is able to stand a vacuum of 75 cm. of mercury without showing any leakage. The arrangement is the same as described by Mukherjee and co-workers (*Indian J. Agric. Sci.*, 1932, 2, 638 ; 1936, 6, 577).

The titration Cell.—The titration cell is of the same type as described by Mukherjee and co-workers (*loc. cit.*).

Potentiometric Measurements.—A Cambridge potentiometer reading up to 0.2 milli-volt and a Leeds and Northrup galvanometer of high current sensitivity (4×10^{-11} amp.) were employed. The normal calomel half cell was used as the reference electrode.

Conductivity Measurements.—The source of A. C. was a Vreeland oscillator working at 500 and 1000 cycles per second. A recalibrated Curtis coil resistance box and a Leeds and Northrup marble drum bridge were used in the assembly. An air condenser of adjustable capacity was connected in parallel with the resistance box in order to balance the capacity of the cell.

Precautions against Electrical Leakages.—For preventing electrical leakages, which are often very troublesome, the following precautions were taken: (a) The experimental table was covered with an earthed metal sheet. (b) All electrical connections were made with lead covered Henley wires, the outer covers being earth connected. (c) All exposed terminals, etc., were protected with insulating tapes and covered with earthed copper gauze.

The Hydrogen Generator.—Hydrogen gas was obtained by the electrolysis of caustic soda solution in a U-tube with platinum electrodes. The gas was purified by passing through concentrated sulphuric acid, soda lime, then through a tube containing copper gauze heated in an electrical furnace (400°), and through purest soda lime and conductivity water, and finally through the experimental liquid before it passed into the titration vessel.

All the measurements were carried out in a water thermostat provided with an electrical heater and thermoregulator at a temperature of $35^\circ + 0.04^\circ$.

R E S U L T S A N D D I S C U S S I O N .

Absolute Value of the p_n of the Sols.

It has been observed with silicic acid sols (*loc. cit.*) that the p_n values of the sols as obtained from the E.M.F. of the hydrogen electrode sometimes show irregular variations. Cleansing and replatinisation of the electrodes

sometimes, though not always, improve matters. The difference in the initial values, however do not materially affect the determination of the total acidity from the titration curves. Similar irregular variations of the initial p_n have been observed also in the case of palmitic acid sols. The p_n was in some cases measured with the quinhydrone electrode for comparison. In the following table are given the observed p_n values for some of the sols on different days. In this table E has the same significance as in the equation,

$$p_n = \frac{E}{0.0001984 T} \quad \dots (i)$$

for both the hydrogen and quinhydrone electrodes. The E.M.F. of the normal calomel half cell against the normal hydrogen electrode has been taken to be 0.2823 volt at 35°.

TABLE I

Sol A				Sol B			
p_n		E		p_n		E	
Pt _n ₂	Q _n						
5.28		0.3226		4.92		0.3006	
	5.22		0.3189		4.78		0.2929
5.34		0.3263		5.00		0.3055	
5.34		0.3263		4.08		0.2993	
5.23		0.3195			4.77		0.2914
5.25		0.3208		4.97		0.3037	
5.11		0.3122			4.61		0.2817
5.19		0.3171		4.70		0.2872	
Mean 5.26		0.3171		Mean 4.88	4.72	0.2981	0.2883
Sol C				Sol D			
p_n		E		p_n		E	
Pt _n ₂	Q _n						
5.48		0.3348			5.10		0.3116
5.45		0.3330			4.90		0.2994
5.10		3.3116		5.00		0.3055	
4.94		0.3019		5.00		0.3055	
4.91		0.2990		5.07		0.3098	
5.15		0.3147		Mean 5.023	5.00	0.3069	0.3055
5.25		0.3195					
5.085		0.3107					
Mean 5.17		0.3160					

The p_H of these sols is near about 5.0. It appears that the p_H (for sols A, B and C) gradually tends to diminish with time and reaches a value in the neighbourhood of 5.0. The maximum difference between the mean p_H values obtained with the hydrogen and quinhydrone electrodes is 0.16 p_H unit representing a difference of 10 m. volts. In the majority of cases, the variations of the individual values of E obtained with the hydrogen electrodes from the mean values, do not exceed 5 m. volts, except in sol C, where the variations are generally larger. While the agreement should be considered satisfactory for such systems it is desirable to obtain E.M.F. values reproducible within 0.1 to 0.5 m. volt, as otherwise the calculated activity is liable to a large error.

For checking the reliability of the experimental arrangement and of the electrodes, a number of measurements were made in HCl solutions of several concentrations. The following table gives the observed p_H values and the values of E as defined above. The third column gives the difference in the values of E for the hydrogen and quinhydrone electrodes.

TABLE II.

	E		Diff. in m. v.		p_H	
	Pt _{H₂}	Q _H	$E_{Pt_{H_2}}$	$- E_{Q_H}$	Pt _{H₂}	Q _H
(1)	0.1301	0.1289		1.2	2.129	2.11
(2)	0.1777	0.1793		1.6	2.908	2.935
(3)	0.1845	0.1839		0.6	3.02	3.01
(4)	0.2447	0.2428		1.9	4.005	3.974
(5)	0.2477	0.2497		2.0	4.054	4.087
(6)	0.2517	0.2533		1.6	4.12	4.08
(7)	0.2609	0.2593		1.6	4.27	4.26
(8)	0.3031	0.3018		1.3	4.96	4.94

In two instances, a difference of about 3 m.v. was observed between the two electrodes. It will be seen that with the precautions which have been adopted, the hydrogen electrode is fairly satisfactory. The larger variation of the p_H of the sols should perhaps be attributed to the difficulties in the attainment of equilibrium with hydrogen gas and the hydrogen ions on the surface of the electrode when the latter is immersed in the sol.

Titration of Palmitic Acid Sols with Bases.

Figures * 1, 2 and 3 show the titration curves of palmitic acid sol A with ammonia (curves 1 and 1', Figs 1 and 2), caustic soda (curves 2 and 2', Figs. 1 and 3), calcium hydroxide (curve 3, Fig. 1) and baryta (curves 4 and 4', Fig. 1). The potentiometric and conductometric titration curves of sol B (curves 5 and 5') with baryta are given in Fig. 5.

The shapes of the potentiometric titration curves as well as the values of the total acidity calculated from the inflexion points in these curves vary with the base employed for the titration. The total acidity values of sol A calculated from the curves are given in Table III.

TABLE III.

Total acidity in normality $\times 10^5$.

$\text{NH}_4\text{OH.}$	NaOH.	$\text{Ba(OH)}_2.$
1.2 (curve ** 1 or 1')	1.9 (curve 2)	10.5 (curve 4)

* In these and in subsequent figures the abscissæ represent nx/v where n is the concentration of the electrolyte in normality, x its volume added and v , the resulting volume (initial volume $+x$) of the titrant.

** It is not possible to calculate the total acidity accurately from the potentiometric curve. This value has been calculated from the minimum point in the corresponding conductometric titration curve as this appears to agree with the inflexion point in the potentiometric curve.

In the potentiometric titration curves with caustic soda, calcium hydroxide and baryta, an initial rise of p_H is followed by a region of buffer action and then by a second steep rise. The point of inflexion in the final rising portion has been used for calculating the total acidity. Beyond the inflexion point, the slope of the curve gradually diminishes. The buffering observed in the titration curves for calcium hydroxide and barium hydroxide is very strong and occurs between p_H 6.0 and 6.5. In the curves 3 and 4 (Fig. 1) the slope vanishes altogether in this region. In the curve for caustic soda, the region of buffer action is much shorter and occurs near p_H 6.0. The indication of a strong buffer action is altogether absent in the case of ammonia. In this curve (no. 1) a weak inflexion is observed at p_H about 6.3 and then the p_H rises sharply to about 7.5. The slope of the curve thereafter rapidly diminishes showing a strong buffer action.

Curves 3 for calcium hydroxide and curve 4 for baryta are of the same nature and run almost parallel. Their displacement appears mainly to result from the difference in the initial p_H values and the hydrogen electrodes in the two cases appear to have maintained a nearly constant difference of potential during the titrations. Curve 4 in Fig. 1 represents a titration which was carried out with larger additions of baryta, keeping the interval between the successive additions constant. The higher slope in the middle portion indicates a non-attainment of equilibrium with the added base.

FIG. 3.
Palmitic acid sol A + KOH.

FIG. 4.
Palmitic acid sol B + baryta.

On titrating sol A with a concentrated solution of caustic soda (curves 6 and 6', Fig. 5) the middle flat portion of the curve is completely suppressed on account of the larger additions of the alkali.

The conductometric titration curve of sol A with ammonia (Curve 1', Fig. 2) has a fairly sharp minimum which agrees with the point of inflexion (not very sharp) in the potentiometric curve. With caustic soda, the conductometric curve has a rounded minimum (curve 2', Fig. 9). This rounded portion corresponds with the region of buffer action in the potentiometric curve. With baryta the conductometric titration curve (curve 5', Fig. 4) has a sharp lowering and then a region of almost constant specific conductivity in agreement with the flat portion in the p_H curve (curve 5, Fig. 4).

Total Acidity as Calculated from the Titration Curves and the Stoichiometric Content of Palmitic Acid in the Sol.

The palmitic acid contents of two sols have been compared with the titrable acids in the sols as calculated from the titration curves (*vide* Table IV). The palmitic acid was extracted from the sol with ether (100 c.c. of ether to 500 c.c. of the sol) and was weighed after evaporation to dryness in a vacuum desiccator.

TABLE IV.

	Total acid ($N \times 10^5$) (By titration with baryta).	Palmitic acid ($N \times 10^5$) (By extraction).
Sol E	19.0	21.9
Sol F	16.2 14.3	15.0
	} Average = 15.2	

Considering the small quantities of acid involved in the extraction, the agreement between the two sets of values should be regarded as satisfactory. In the titrations with baryta practically all the palmitic acid has thus reacted with the base at the inflection point.

Titration and Back Titration.

Palmitic acid sol C was titrated with baryta up to p_H 8.34 (beyond the point of inflexion which occurs near p_H 7.0) and then the sol was left overnight in the titration vessel after carefully sealing up with pure paraffin wax all openings of the titration cell so as to avoid ingress of carbon dioxide from the air. The next morning the sol was titrated with hydrochloric acid (curves 7 and 7', Fig. 6).

FIG. 5.
Palmitic acid sol A + KOH

FIG. 6.
Palmitic acid sol C

The initial p_H on the second day was only 7.05. As the leakage of carbon dioxide in the cell is not likely, the lowering of p_H should be ascribed to a slow reaction with the excess of baryta. The back titration curve (curve 7', Fig. 6) has nearly the same form as the original titration curve and shows a striking parallelism with it. The back reaction, *viz.*, the formation of palmitic acid and barium chloride by the action of hydrochloric acid on barium palmitate is also attended with buffer action. The original reaction is thereby shown to be reversible. It may be mentioned that the sol had coagulated on standing overnight in excess of baryta. It is significant that the titration curves of the colloidal solution (baryta titration) and of the suspension of the coagulum (back titration with HCl) which certainly constitutes a heterogeneous system show such close resemblance.

Effect of Neutral Salts.

Palmitic acid sol B was titrated with potassium chloride and sol C with barium chloride (curves 8, 9 and 9', Fig. 7) and sol D also with barium chloride* (curve 11, Fig. 8). A similar titration of a hydrochloric acid solution of approximately the same p_H as the sol with barium chloride was carried out for comparison (curves 10, Fig. 7).

Potassium chloride produces only a slight change of p_H (0.04 p_H unit on the first addition, $nX/v = 0.002N$) and on further additions, the p_H re-

* This titration was stopped after the p_H came down to 4.44 and the titration cell was kept sealed overnight. On resuming the titration on the next morning, the p_H was found to be 4.16 and did not change on further additions of the salt.

mains practically unchanged. Barium chloride on the other hand produced a larger change of hydrogen ion activity. The lowering of p_H is sharper at the beginning but the rate of change diminishes with increasing concentration of the added salt. In each of the barium chloride curves, a break in the slope is observed which suggests that the reaction occurs in two stages. The position of the break, however, appears to bear no relation to the hydrogen ion concentration of the sol or its palmitic acid content.

FIG. 7.

[Curve 8 refers to sol B + KCl; 9 & 9' to sol C + BaCl₂ and 10 to HCl + BaCl₂ respectively.]

FIG. 8.

Sols D and G were mixed with barium chloride so as to make the sol decinormal with respect to the salt in each case and left overnight. The mixture was titrated with baryta the following day. The titration curves of the two sols and of their mixtures with barium chloride are given in Figs. 9 (curves 12 and 13) and in Fig. 10 (curves 16 and 17).

The shapes of the titration curves in the presence of barium chloride resemble that of a strong acid and have steeper inflexions.* The titration curves of the ultrafiltrates of sols D and G (curves 14 and 18) and of their ultrafiltrates in the presence of 0.1 N barium chloride (curves 15 and 19) are also given in the above figures. Curves 14 and 15 show buffer action between p_H 5.4 and 6.4. A thin ultrafilter membrane of finer pore size

* At the beginning of curve 11, there is a short flat portion and in the curve 12 a short rise in the same region. These features are absent in the curves for sol G.

was used for sol G with the result that this feature is absent in the titration curves (18 and 19) of the ultrafiltrates. It appears that in the former case, the ultrafiltrates contained fine colloidal particles of palmitic acid which had passed through the membrane.

FIG. 9.
Palmitic acid sol D.

The effect of the addition of barium chloride to palmitic acid sols on their free and total acidities and on those of their ultrafiltrates will be seen in Table V.

TABLE V.

	Without addition of salt			In the presence of 0.1 N-BaCl ₂		
	pH.	$a_n \times 10^5$.	Total acidity ($N \times 10^5$).	pH.	$a_n \times 10^5$.	Total acidity ($N \times 10^5$).
Sol D	5.02	9.98	19.5	4.14	7.24	16.5
Ultrafiltrate	4.87?	—	3.5	4.40	3.68	9.0
Sol G	5.17	0.676	12.8	4.64	9.29	11.7
Ultrafiltrate	5.43	0.372	2.3	4.70	2.00	5.7

The total acidities of the sols in presence of barium chloride are somewhat less than those of the pure sols. The hydrogen ion activities of the sols in presence of barium chloride, though higher than those of the pure sols, are less than the total acidities of the sols (37% in the case of sol D and 18% in the case of sol G of their respective total acidities). This shows that at this stage the majority of the hydrogen ions are not free, *i.e.* are osmotically inactive, although they can react with hydroxyl ions at a lower p_H level (*vide*, curve 17) than in the pure sol.

FIG. 10.

*Palmitic acid sol G.**Palmitic Acid Sol as a Single Phase System.*

The point of view that colloidal solutions can be treated as single phase systems appears at first sight to receive support from the titration curves of palmitic acid sols, especially with the alkaline earth hydroxides, which resemble to some extent those of weak monobasic acids with a strong alkali. It will be shown below that the resemblance is only superficial.

Variations of the Total Acidity and the Difference in the Forms of the Titration Curves obtained with Different Bases.

It has already been pointed out that the total acidities calculated from the points of inflexion of the titration curves vary with the base employed.

Iyer (*Half yearly J. Mysore Univ.*, 1932, 6, 1) found a similar difference between the potentiometric titration curves of stearic acid hydrosols with caustic soda and baryta. In the titration of a weak acid with caustic soda which results in the formation of a soluble salt, part of the added alkali will remain unneutralised on account of hydrolysis and the p_H will rise initially. The dissociation of the remaining acid will be depressed due to the increased concentration of the anions and the 'buffer capacity' of the system will increase reaching a maximum value at the point of half neutralisation. The titration curve will thus have a comparatively flat middle portion. But the final point of inflexion will occur when the acid is completely neutralised and this point, as a result of hydrolysis, will lie in the alkaline region. The observed difference in the total acidity values with different bases is not expected of a truly dissolved acid when the resulting salts are soluble. Besides, the point of inflexion in the titration curve with caustic soda lies below p_H 7.0.

FIG. 11.

If we regard palmitic acid sol as a single phase system, its neutralisation with baryta or calcium hydroxide, which form insoluble salts with palmitic acid, should resemble the analogous case of the neutralisation of dissolved citric acid with calcium hydroxide. The insoluble calcium citrate formed during the titration separates out as a solid phase and the hydrogen ion concentration of the solution at any stage is determined by the concentration of the citric acid left unneutralised. No sudden rise of p_H should therefore be observed during the titration until at the equivalence point the p_H rises sharply similar to what happens on the addition of calcium hydroxide to

pure water. The observed forms of the titration curves are not in agreement with the expected behaviour. Further evidence will presently be given against the hypothesis, that the colloidal solution of palmitic acid behaves as a single phase system.

*Variability of the Dissociation Constant Calculated
from the Titration Curves.*

In the dissolved state palmitic acid is known to be a weak acid. The homologues of acetic acid up to decolic acid have dissociation constants not differing greatly from that of acetic acid, *viz.*, 1.7×10^{-5} . McBain and Buckingham (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 2688) has assumed the value 10^{-5} for the dissociation constant of palmitic acid at 90° for making approximate calculations.

The values of α , the ratio of free acidity and total acidity, for a number of palmitic acid sols calculated from the equation :

$$K = \frac{\alpha^2 c}{1 - \alpha} \quad \dots \quad (ii)$$

are given in Table VI. The total acidities used in the calculations are those obtained from the potentiometric titration curves with baryta. The dissociation constants calculated from equation (iii) and from the titration curves at the points of one fourth, half and three fourths neutralisations using the Henderson equation :

$$p_H = p_K + \log \frac{[\text{Salt}] + [A]}{[\text{Acid}] - [A]} \quad \dots \quad (iii)$$

are also given in the same table.

TABLE VI.

	Acidity ($N \times 10^5$)		$K \times 10^7$				
	Free.	Total.	From eqn.	At 1/4 neutralisation.	At 1/2 neutralisation.	At 3/4 neutralisation.	
Sol A	0.575	10.5	5.48	3.4	1.95	3.39	17.0
Sol B	1.59	14.6	10.9	19.5	1.95	4.79	10.0
Sol C	0.851	15.3	5.54	5.90	1.41	3.16	8.51
Sol D	0.980	18.8	5.21	5.30	1.95	4.47	8.91
Sol E	0.589	19.0	3.10	1.90	3.16	7.08	17.4
Sol F	0.631	15.3	4.13	2.66	1.86	4.57	11.5
Sol G	0.676	13.7	5.60	4.00	1.82	5.01	14.5

The calculated dissociation constants are mostly of the order of 10^{-7} and are lower than the probable value for the acid in the dissolved condition. The numerical values of K for the different sols, however, show large variations. Even for the same sol, the dissociation constant calculated from the titration curve increases steadily from the point of one fourth neutralisation to that of three fourths neutralisation. Such variation denotes that the rate of change of p_H in the titration curve is less than what should be expected in that of a weak acid in true solution.

In the potentiometric titration curve of a weak monobasic acid by a strong alkali, the slope of the curve at the point of half neutralisation has been shown by Auerbach and Smolezyk (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1924, 110, 65), to be independent of the dissociation constant of the acid. They obtain for the slope the expression

$$\frac{dp_H}{dx} = \frac{1.74}{x_a} \quad \dots (iv)$$

where x_a is the volume of the base required to reach the point of inflexion. Table VII gives the actual values of the slope at the point of half neutralisation in the titration curves with baryta and those calculated from equation (iv) for a number of sols. The slopes are expressed in terms of p_H units per c.c. of the added base.

TABLE VII.

	$\frac{dp_H}{dx}$ (obs.).	$\frac{dp_H}{dx}$ (calc.).
Sol A	{ 0.375 0.00	1.58
Sol B	0.320	1.20
Sol C	0.150	1.16
Sol D	0.115	0.982
Sol E	0.537	1.83
Sol F	0.111	1.074
Sol G	0.078	1.36

The observed slope is always less than the calculated value of the minimum slope and is zero in curves 3 and 4 for sol A in Fig. 1. The titration curves thus show that the course of neutralisation of colloid

solutions of palmitic acid is quite different from that of an acid in true solution.

Palmitic Acid Sol as a Two-phase System.

The behaviour of palmitic acid sol during titrations will be better understood if we regard it as a heterogeneous rather than a homogeneous system. The colloidal particles of palmitic acid may be regarded as constituting the solid phase in thermodynamic equilibrium with its saturated solution in water. On the addition of baryta to the sol there will be a lowering of the hydrogen ion concentration and a corresponding increase of the concentration of palmitate ions till the solubility product of barium palmitate is exceeded. The salt will now begin to form a second solid phase. The system will consist of three components existing in four phases (including the vapour) and will be univariant. At a constant temperature therefore (since the pressure may also be assumed to remain constant) the neutralisation should proceed at a constant composition of the system (Nernst, "Theoretical Chemistry," 10th German Ed., 1923, p. 626), *i.e.*, at a constant p_{π} . When one of the solid phases, namely, palmitic acid disappears, the system becomes bivariant and the p_{π} increases on the addition of the base. Since the salt is insoluble, there will be no perceptible hydrolysis and an inflexion will occur in the titration curve at the point of complete neutralisation of the acid at the neutral p_{π} . All these features are corroborated by the potentiometric titration curves 3 and 4 of palmitic acid sol A, where the titrations have been carried out under equilibrium conditions. The slight rise of p_{π} in the middle portions of the other curves must be attributed to the non-attainment of equilibrium with the added base. The only point of difference which is to be observed is that beyond the points of inflexions, the titration curves show indication of a reaction of the base with the insoluble salt.

On the addition of barium chloride to a palmitic acid sol, the insoluble barium palmitate is formed and simultaneously an equivalent amount of hydrochloric acid is liberated in accordance with the equation,

The system has now four components existing in four phases and is bivariant and at a constant temperature and pressure can remain in equilibrium with varying compositions of the liquid phase. Actually the p_{π} diminishes with increasing concentrations of barium chloride.

If S_1 and S_2 denote the solubility products of palmitic acid and barium palmitate respectively, the following relations follow from the law of mass action:

$$[H^+]. [P^-] = S_1 \quad \dots \quad (vi)$$

and $[Ba^{++}]. [P^-]^2 = S_2 \quad \dots \quad (vii)$

whence $\frac{\sqrt{[Ba^{++}]}}{[H^+]} = S_2/S_1 = Z \text{ (constant)} \quad \dots \quad (viii)$

Thus, under equilibrium conditions the concentration of hydrogen ions should vary proportionately with the square root of the molar concentration of the barium ions in the solution. The values of Z calculated* at different points in the titration curves (curves 20 and 21 for sol C and curve 22 for sol D) with barium chloride are plotted against the equivalent concentration of barium chloride nx/v in Figure 11. In each of the curves Z rises initially and after a break in the slope tends to become constant. In curve 20 it actually becomes constant after the addition of 0.01N-barium chloride with the exception of one stray value. In the other curves Z continues to increase, though slowly. That the variations of the value of Z indicate a true thermodynamic equilibrium between the different phases has not been established under these conditions.

The results given above show definitely that colloidal solution of palmitic acid differ in their electrochemical properties in some essential respects from acids in true solution. It has also been shown that the shapes of the titration curves with calcium hydroxide or baryta and the interactions of the sols with barium chloride are, barring some irregularities, in agreement with the expected behaviour if the colloidal solution be regarded as a heterogeneous system. The colloidal particles are to be considered as constituting a solid phase which is in equilibrium with its saturated solution. The irregular features are: (a) the slopes of the titration curves obtained with baryta at the point of half neutralisation are not always zero

* In calculating these values the concentration of barium ions have been obtained by subtracting half of the increase of the hydrogen ions concentration of the sol from molar concentration of the barium chloride added to the sol. The assumptions have been made that (1) the observed increase in the number of hydrogen ions in the sol is accompanied with the disappearance of an equivalent number of barium ions from the solution and (2) the activity coefficient of barium chloride at the concentrations involved is unity.

and (b) the value of the ratio $\sqrt{[B^{++}/H^+]}$ does not always remain constant during the titration of the sol with barium chloride. The probable causes of these irregularities and also the mechanism of the interactions taking place between palmitic acid sols and bases and salts are discussed below.

It has been pointed out already in a previous section that a difference between the slopes of the titration curves of sol A with baryta is observed on changing the rate of addition of the base. It shows that the interactions taking place between the sol and the base are slow and the non-attainment of equilibrium under the conditions of experiment may lead to irregular results. There is another factor which may impart characteristic properties to colloidal solutions, namely, the electrical double layer surrounding the colloidal particles (Mukherjee, Mitra and Mukherjee, *loc. cit.*). The negative charge of colloidal particles of acidic substances originate from the existence of primarily adsorbed anions on their surface. An equivalent amount of hydrogen ions are present in the double layer, partly in the mobile condition and partly as secondarily adsorbed ions. Cations of an added electrolyte will displace the mobile hydrogen ions by diffusion into the double layer and may also get adsorbed on the surface and simultaneously displace the bound hydrogen ions. The ion pair formed by the metallic cation and the primarily adsorbed anion may or may not be stable on the surface depending on several factors. These factors are :—

(a) The lattice energy of the primarily adsorbed anions, *i.e.*, the forces holding these ions on to the neighbouring ions in the interior of the particles.

(b) The stability of the primarily adsorbed ions in the free state in solution.

(c) The solubility of the salt formed by the ions constituting the ion pair if it separates as a solid phase during the experiment.

(d) The lattice energy of the crystals of this salt. A relatively large lattice energy of the primarily adsorbed anions and a low stability of these ions in a state of solution would favour the formation of stable ion pairs on the surface, while under the reverse conditions the latter will split off from the surface and pass into the solution either as a dissolved molecule or forming a separate solid phase when its solubility product is exceeded. Again, a large difference between the lattice energies of the resulting salt and the primarily adsorbed anion or a low solubility of the salt will help the ion pair to pass into the solution. In the case where the ion pairs are stable on the surface, the electrical double layer and not the core of the

particles is in equilibrium with the solution. The conditions underlying the classical phase rule are, therefore, not satisfied and the system behaves differently. On the other hand, if the ion pair passes into the solution as soon as it is formed, the colloidal particles as a whole takes part in the equilibrium and the colloidal solution behaves as a true heterogeneous system.

There is evidence to show that an electrical double layer exists surrounding the colloidal particle of palmitic acid. Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Bhabak (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 379) have shown from micro-cathaphoretic experiments that these colloidal particles are negatively charged. Wiegner and Pallmann ("Verhandlungen der internationalen Bodenkundlichen Gesellschaft," 1929, pp. 92-243) observed that suspensions of palmitic acid in water have higher hydrogen ion activities than the clear supernatant liquids. Again, it will be seen from Table V in this paper that the hydrogen ion activities of mixtures of sols D and G with 0.1N barium chloride are appreciably higher than those of their ultrafiltrates.* Such observations indicate that mobile hydrogen ions are present in the electrical double layer surrounding the colloidal particles. Here the primarily adsorbed ions are the palmitate ions. These ions are stable in alkaline solutions. In very weakly acid solutions they are stable at such a low concentration which obtains in the solution in equilibrium with the solid acid and barium palmitate. Besides, large differences between the lattice energies of solid palmitic acid and barium palmitate are also probable. On interaction with baryta, the ion pairs formed by the barium ions and the primarily adsorbed palmitate ions, therefore, split off as barium palmitate molecules and a separate phase is formed when the solubility product is exceeded. The system, as has been shown in a previous section, now behaves as a heterogeneous system obeying the phase rule and the law of mass action.

On the addition of barium chloride to the sol, the mobile hydrogen ions are displaced from the double layer and at the same time barium ions are adsorbed to form ion pairs. As in the titration of the sol with baryta, these ion pairs split off to form barium palmitate molecules as a separate phase and hydrochloric acid is liberated in accordance with equation (v). The increase in the concentration of hydrogen ions renders the palmitate ions less stable in solution and at the same time causes the displacement of

* It will also be seen from Table V that sol G has a lower p_H than its ultrafiltrate but the reverse is observed in the case of sol D. The ultrafiltrates being extremely dilute unbuffered solution, the p_H values obtained for them are subject to a greater uncertainty than for the sols. Presumably in the above case the p_H of the ultrafiltrate of sol D is somewhat in error.

the hydrogen ions on the surface by barium ions more difficult. Consequently the reaction with barium chloride remains incomplete. This is seen from the fact that the free acidity of the mixture of the sol with barium chloride is less than the total acidity of the sol. From the results so far obtained, it is difficult to decide whether in the interaction of palmitic acid sol with barium chloride a thermodynamic equilibrium between the acid and the salt in the solid phases is at all established. The non-uniform nature of the curves in Fig. 11 shows that the reaction is of a somewhat complex nature. Further work on this problem is in progress.

The lower value of the total acidity obtained by titrating a mixture of palmitic acid sol and barium chloride with baryta than that obtained by titrating the pure sol with the same base indicates that a portion of the acid remains unneutralised at the inflexion point in the former case. The sol coagulates in the presence of barium chloride and the aggregates probably enclose some of the acid molecules which are prevented from reacting with the added base by a layer of barium palmitate molecules covering the surface.

In the interaction of the sol with potassium chloride the mobile hydrogen ions are displaced into the intermicellary liquid but the adsorption of potassium ions does not proceed to any great extent on account of their low adsorbability. Again, potassium palmitate being soluble in water, the ion pairs formed will not appreciably pass into solution as the palmitate ions are unstable in such solutions at high concentrations. Consequently there is only a very small change in the hydrogen ion activity of the sol.

Ammonia being a weak base, ammonium palmitate is easily hydrolysed in solution. Ammonium ions are also relatively weakly adsorbed. Very little reaction is therefore indicated in the titration curve with ammonium hydroxide up to p_H 7.5. The strong buffer action which is observed above this p_H shows that palmitate ions are now stable and the neutralisation of the acid molecules proceeds. The colloidal particles gradually dissolve at this stage.

Sodium palmitate is stable and less hydrolysed than ammonium palmitate in solution. But it appears that the reaction is not strong enough below p_H 7 to dissolve the particles. The point of inflexion in the rising portion of the titration curve which also corresponds with the minimum of the conductometric titration curve, probably denotes the neutralisation of the dissolved palmitic acid in the sol. The p_H at the point of neutralisation gives an indication of the strength of the acid ($p_K = p_H = 7.8$) in the dissolved condition. Further reaction of the colloidal particles with caustic soda takes place at a higher p_H level.

S U M M A R Y .

1. Irregular variations of the p_n of palmitic acid sols, measured with the hydrogen and quinhydrone electrodes, have been observed although the same experimental arrangement gives satisfactory results in dilute solutions of hydrochloric acid.

2. The forms of the electrometric and conductometric titration curves of palmitic acid sols and the total acidities calculated therefrom vary with the base employed for the titration. The latter vary in the order :

The total acidity obtained from the baryta titration curves agrees with the analytical concentration of palmitic acid in the sol.

3. The forms of the titration curves differ from that of an acid in true solution, whether the resulting salt is assumed to be soluble or insoluble. The calculated values of the dissociation constant are much lower than the probable value for the acid in the dissolved condition. The slopes of the titration curves with baryta at the point of half neutralisation are smaller than the theoretically calculated values for weak acids in true solution.

4. The titration curves with baryta and the interactions with barium chloride are, excepting some minor irregular features, in agreement with the expected behaviour assuming the sol to be a two phase system.

5. The mechanism of the interactions of colloidal particles of palmitic acid with different electrolytes has been discussed with reference to the electrical double layer surrounding the particles.

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